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The Bewitching New Digital World and the Human Experience of Time

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Abstract: The growing new digital world has changed our experience of time. Time today is not felt as irreversible and linear. We seem to be lost in an intensive now. We are mindlessly living in a now time. The moment has become intense and we are moving in all directions within the focal point of now. The arrival of the smart phone has amplified this experience of time. We have to make responses at the speed of a blink of an eye. This means it is difficult to offer a reflected or rationally considered responses to our condition. This is why this study proposes the adoption of reflexive responses through the cultivation of phronesis as well as embrace a habit that thinks what one does.

Keywords: Digital world, Electracy, Post-literacy, Time, Phygital, Phronesis, Communication-technologies

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The growing new digital world has changed our experience of time. Time today is not felt as irreversible and linear. We seem to be lost in an intensive now. We are mindlessly living in a now time. The moment has become intense and we are moving in all directions within the focal point of now. The arrival of the smart phone has amplified this experience of time. We have to give ourselves responses at the speed of a blink of an eye. This study attempts to understand this changed temporal experience of humanity. We begin with an analysis of the transformed experience of time and propose a need for the cultivation of phronesis to face the bubble of the now-time (Kozhamthadam, 2015). Next. We turn to the Grammatology of Derrida to examine how the new Digital world is writing (shaping)our life and thus invite us to trace critical ways of resistance. Finally, we take the new experience of time head and demonstrate that we have stopped thinking about what we are doing. We end with a conviction that it is only with the cultivation of thinking about what we are doing that we can respond to this new experience of temporality.

Hauntology of the Digital World of Images

Every invention, process, system or program includes its own disaster. This is a standard Hegelian doctrine. The inventors of the ship also invented the ship wreck. There are always seeds of destruction in everything. The fact that we have stepped into the internet era, we have recognised that it has blessings as well as curses. One of the issues that reveal to us the dark side of the web is that it traps us in the present moment. The moment that is now has become intensive and everything is compressed into it. Oral societies ran on a cyclical time and the literate ones ran on linear time. But something has drastically changed around us. We have entered what Gregory Ulmer calls electracy (Joseph, 1997). Electracy runs on the now-time. Everything happens in an instant. Most of our decisions on the net do not evolve deliberative thinking. They happen on the spot in an intense moment. This means our

decisions are based on intuitive beliefs that Malcolm Gladwell (2019) calls ‘blink’. We work in an instance of immediacy. My book, *Being Human in a World of Artificial Intelligence*, invites us to cultivate prudence that Aristotle calls *phronesis* so that our instantaneous or reflexive actions still stay ethical or moral. This means we need a new discipline of the mind that will enable us to deal with a culture that is trapped in a now-time.

Literacy is not just a technology of alphabets but is a school that forms our thinking as well as shapes our identity. We are fast moving away from the world of the alphabets and are gravitating towards the fast-paced dynamic digital world. Hence, we need a mode of classification of the digital images. It has to do with what the concept did to literacy. Concepts gave us ways of organizing things according to essences and accidents. Electracy needs an image category that will enable us to make decisions in the now-time. This is why I have argued that we need practical reason or *phronesis* to respond to the challenges of the now-time. Some scholars think that *phronesis* is thought in the future perfect tense and is concerned with what will have been. This means as prudence, it relies on the lessons of the past but finds creative ways of concretising those general principles in the present so that a future is hoped to be perfect. This means that the general or universal norm that is learnt from the past is to be applied case by case. In each case, the universal may modify differently to suit the specific condition. Such wisdom was called *phronesis* by Aristotle. *Phronesis* though a chief form of practical reason did not disassociate from the pure reason. It has been argued that dismantling of the relation between pure reason and practical reason began with the renaissance in Europe. With modernity, there came a slow death of practical reason. In fact, G.W. Leibniz praised the Chinese civilization for its superiority over the Western civilization in the area of practical reason (Horyna, 2020).

The now-time is intensely haunting us and the fact that we have no practical reason to assist us, we are heading towards a disaster. We have seen how fake news has instantaneously converted unsuspecting humans into lynch mobs. We are seeing a mass hysteria in political rallies where people and the politicians gather in large numbers without any fear of Covid-19. This mass frenzy as well as individual addictive attachments to the web show that we need to still find an ethical response to our life that is frozen into an intensive moment. We are indeed struck into ‘out of joint time’ that Derrida call’s aporia (Hart, 2007). Such time that is experienced as ‘out of joint’ actually opens our possibilities of being in the world. This is why we are haunted by the potentials of that time. Therefore, we need a new way of approaching the dance of images or the choreography of images in the internet. Ulmer suggests that *chora* (Greek word for space, since Plato) has a potency to be what topic has become for literacy. We can see how a topic becomes a choreography for related concepts in an organized constellation. This means the choreography of the images becomes an oracle that calls the individual on the web into being. We may understand it as a call or sense of being addressed with help of Luis Althusser who teaches us that we are interpellated subjects (Althusser, n.d).

Following Althusser, we can think that the dynamic choreography of sound, visual as well as verbal images say ‘Hey You’(address us) and hold our attention for a moment and we enjoy the dance of these images. But there are times when such images can lead us to a disaster like the way fake news converts unsuspecting humans into lynch murders. I like to think that the digital has become phygital (Welsh, 2021). We already have the internet of things. But more critically, the digital has come to become hybridized alongside our culture. This is why we can see how people succumb to mass propaganda and manipulations. The television debates on television are full of heat and no light nor insight. May be we can also see that it is for the reason stated above that people vote for notes. Usually notes come in the dead of the night and there is no time to think.

Pure reason has no room to guide the people so they mindlessly end up voting for notes inviting their own enslavement. The same is true about fanaticism where one has already surrendered his/ her mind to the narrow, narcissist, sadist and masochist beliefs. We can see such extremism visible in political popularism across the globe. This means that cyclic time and linear time has stopped influencing us. We are trapped in the now-time. Time stops for us; it becomes intense and offers us possibilities of being in the world. Trapped in a Now-time we cannot postpone our response. It has to be instantaneous. Our old ethical responses require us to undergo critical analysis. This requires time and we do not have this luxury. Lest our responses are driven only by our likes and dislikes (aesthetical tastes), we need to cultivate phronesis that will enable us to respond ethically and reflexively to our fast spaced yet paradoxically trapped in the now-time world.

Time for Grammatology: Decoding the Grammar and the Grammatics of Life

Derrida's method of deconstruction has paid rich dividends in circles of critical thinking. While its importance still remains, it may be important to enter his grammatology or the science of writing and examine its potency to critical thinking. Given the communicative technologies and the scope of the internet in our life, a return to grammatology (study of writings) is perhaps the most important and urgent turn that we have to take. This does not mean that deconstruction has reached a point of exertion and there is no light nor emancipative insight within it. While deconstruction has several fertile and critical applications, we turn to grammatology in order to deal with the play of signs in the world of digital images and the internet. To succeed in this effort, we have to turn to writing in its early stage. In order to perform this task, we have overcome blindness that reduces all writing to phoneticization. Derrida teaches that there is also

non-phonetic writings like pictorial, ideographic and symbolic (Scott, 2002). We can come to this realisation only when we enter the early stage of writing. We think that writing is associated with representation of the spoken word. In fact, this reduction of writing to spoken word leads us to consider to be phonic in nature. But this reduction actually limits the domain and power of writing. Even as we are conditioned by this reduction, contrary to our conditioning, the dynamic play of digital images on the internet has deconstructed this belief. Thus, to some extent, the world of the internet has crossed the limits of understanding of the role as well as the scope of writing.

In its early stages, writing was associated with drawing and visual art and had a loose association with speaking. It is the phoneticization of writing that transformed it into a representation of the spoken word alone. This means writing as representation repressed/suppressed its non-phonetic forms. Moreover, there cannot be exact one to one correspondence between the spoken word and the written word. This is because both carry ideographic/ cognitive forms as well as emotive/ affective inflections and hence are not merely verbal in nature. Phoneticization has to linearize writing to make it carry its ideographic forms. The world of digital media has already contested the phoneticization as well as linearization of writing. In many ways it has opened writing to its plural forms and in doing so has broken the chains that constrained our thought. Writing is enabled to embrace mythogram that is not subjected to successivity of the order of the logical time as well as irreversible temporality of the sound or the verbal language. Thus, we have to not only set writing free from speech, but we also have to set it free from its entanglements with phoneticization. Thanks to the dance of digital images in the world of the internet, we have already almost reached this stage. But some of us may be still be thinking that the world is flat even after it is circumnavigated.

Here we follow Derrida to expand the scope of writing so as to embrace the world of play of digital images. The consideration of non-phonetic writings makes room for the dance of signs in the digital world. We name as writing to all that gives rise to an inscription. This means the embrace of writing includes cinematography, choreography as well pictorial, musical and sculptural writings. We may include sport, military as well as political writings. This means grammatology opens us to these multidimensional forms of writings and thus deconstructs singularized, logocentric phonetic writing. Writing is a program. It seems to inundate all writing forms. We have to understand that gramme or graphme is a trace that inhabits all forms of writings both phonetic as well as non-phonetic ones. Hence, all of them can be studied by grammatology. This is why we have to accept that we have the challenge to understand and respond to the world of electracy through grammatology. The play of signs in digital media is a form of writing and can be decoded by following the principles of grammatology. But to fully understand what this dance of signs does to us, we have to enter into the energetics of trace which Derrida radicalizes by introducing Freud's slips of pen and tongue to full domains of writing. This is why choreography of the signs in the digital world produces a surplus and leaves an impact on us through its trace.

In several ways, many of us lament the end of the Book. The habit of reading is dying among people. This is chiefly because of the reign of non-phonetic writings. The libidinal investment in the form of reading has diminished and one can notice a great harvest of libidinal involvement of humans with the digital world. This is why grammatology has become an important key to understand how the new electronic media is writing us and shaping our life. We can be often blinded by the dance of the signs in the digital world and fail to understand how we are made to dance to its tunes. Grammatology as a science of

writing can reveal to us the writing of the images in the digital world as well as how that writing is writing our life. This means grammatology is a pedagogy. The fact that it manifests that the new media is writing our life, effectively enables us to wakefully resist it and take charge of writing our life. There is a difference between being written and writing one script of life. To do this we have to not just consider the cognitive/ideographic but also the energetic/ affective side of the dance of the signs in the world of digital media. This means we have to overcome the logocentrism of the digital world. The digital world, therefore, is messenger, message and massager. This means there are cognitive/ ideographic as well as emotive/ affective sides to the dynamism of the new media. What it does is important along with what it says. This is why we have to move from semiotic hermeneutics to productive hermeneutics. Grammatology includes both semiotic hermeneutics and productive hermeneutics. The rise of the dynamic digital world has hastened the importance of grammatology. To respond to this dance of sense, produced by the dance of sense, we have the challenge to embrace grammatology and see how it is at work everywhere writing the grammar of our life. Only once we move to grammatology, we will be enabled to take charge of not just the grammar but also the grammatics of our life.

New Experience of Time

Communication technologies have become omnipresent because of the smart phone. This condition has transformed our experience of time. Oral societies were based on cyclic time. The spoken word did not enjoy strict relations with the written word in such scenarios. The writing was in the form of drawings and hieroglyphs. The spoken word was very important. It

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being depended on the medium of sound, humans experienced irreversible temporality. This is because human spoken words cannot be recovered once spoken. They exist in an irreversible temporality. But when human words were alphabetized and came to be written, they were freed from the irreversible temporality but got chained to the order of the logic of linearity. We can read the written word and return to the same text again and again. We can see how the sacred texts of the religion are set free from temporal irreversibility but got entangled in linearity and logic that is different from the mythological thinking of the previous stage of humanity. This means with the new experience of time, we also have experienced a leap in our thinking. The written word ushered linear, rational and dialectical thinking while the previous thinking was cyclic and exhibits a different mode of rationality.

With the rise of electracy, (digital world), we have stepped into now-time of great intensity and speed. With this new experience of time, we have moved away from the irreversibility and linearity of time. Everything occurs in the now. We are now imprisoned in the futurism of the instant. The moment I have become pregnant with power and possibilities. Paul Virilio indicates that we are facing an information bomb. He says that the experience of space has also changed (Mambrol, 2018). The tyranny of distance has given way to the tyranny of real-time. We are living as disabled people, doing prosthetic gadgetry of all kinds. Because of this 'now' has almost replaced physical 'here'. Virtual space has come to replace real space. This is why Jean Baudrillard famously and provocatively said that the Gulf war was fought on computers (Wikipedia contributors, 2020). Not just real space has lost its importance, even physical bodies are being replaced by their avatars in the digital world. Erotics of distance is fast derailing human intimacy and attraction. What we are facing is the disappearance of materiality due to excessive digitalization and the hegemony of the now over

history and time of community. We are fast losing our links to our past and the future.

This means our experience of time has changed. We are no longer rigidly enslaved by irreversible and linear time schedules. We have become to embrace flexi-time. Flexi time or work schedules brings the best out of us. We are enabled to work optimally than those who are entangled by the dialectics of the irreversible and linear time. Maybe our attachments to the dialectics of irreversible and linear time refuses to see the change that surrounds us. Technological changes have indeed changed the experience of time. We experience reversible and non-linearity of time on our smart phones. We can rewind, stop and jump to the next item on our smart phone. Time has become elastic and we can stretch it in all direction as we live in a dynamic and intensive now. Some people have moved on with this changed time others are still pulling on with the irreversible and linear time. But moving on as well as staying on have their own costs.

Virilio tells us that virtualization is also invisibilisation (Dawes, 2019). When power becomes virtual it becomes invisible and almost omnipresent. This is why we have to understand how the virtual world has

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its power over us. While we are living in a now-time flowing at a great speed, we have less time to offer our responses and we almost are reduced to automatons who respond mindlessly and mechanically. This is the dark side of the loss of the irreversible and linear experience of time. This experience of time offered us refreshing and reflecting breaks so that we could critically discern our responses. The fast-paced digital world only allows for reflexive response and therefore, we have stepped into a new form of rationality and we may need what Aristotle called phronesis/practical wisdom. Since virtualization has invisibilized space, place

and even our bodies, we have a different mode of politics. We can see how parliament is silenced while mass political rallies as well television debate frenzies have become the order of the day. People are seen to cry slogans of their cultic leader in ecstasy. This means we are trapped in a now bubble and mindlessly support political agenda without knowing that social engineering is producing our responses.

It is important to realise that we are trapped in a bubble of now-time. The instant result culture had predisposed us while the rise of the internet and the communication technologies have imprisoned us into the now-time. We are now set to come full circle into logocentrism. Since we are liberated from both irreversibility and linearity, we are set free to hop in all directions of a focal moment that is now. Hence, it is urgent that we burst the time bubble before it explodes into our face. It has already destroyed our social life (family life) as we now prefer the next best thing to the face-to-face experience. Hence, we have to find ways of disengaging the now-time. Hannah Arendt had lamented that ‘we are losing our ability to think and speak of things nevertheless, we are able to do’ (Popova, 2017). Living in the now-time, we are fast becoming automatons. This is certainly a degradation and enslavement of our humanity.

The emerging world of digital communication technologies is threatening the possibility of politics

Virilio taught us that the emerging world of digital communication technologies is threatening the possibility of politics (Kellner, n.d) We are already seeing it in the form of hysteric masses around a cultic leader replacing debates in the parliament. But what is the way forward to us? It does appear that the way forward is through the internet and not outside it. We cannot change the reality that is around us. Gregory Ulmer certainly gives us the hope that our response to the tyranny of the now-

time is in the internet. What we need is a singular purpose that was set by Arendt in her book, *Human Condition*--- think what we are doing. Therefore, we cannot abdicate our ability to think what we do. Today, humanity needs it more than ever before.

Conclusion

Our study reveals to us that we cannot become passive spectators in our present world. We cannot simply worship a singular phallus and think that all is well in our world as the masses do with their cultic leader. We have to think about what we are doing. Giving up thinking is enslaving and dehumanizing. It is high time that we learn to think again.

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